

Artificial Intelligence Technologies and the Economic Empowerment of Girls and Women: Prospects, Challenges, and Policy Pathways

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping participation, productivity, and outcomes in the economy, with significant implications for the economic empowerment of girls and women. This study adopted a systematic review approach to the potentials, challenges, and policy or governance pathways of gender-sensitive AI applications. Based on the pre-specified inclusion and exclusion criteria, peer-reviewed journal articles as well as policy reports and gray-literature were systematically searched and analysed across relevant databases and institutional homepages. According to the PRISMA 2020 guidelines, 49 studies were identified by a systematic search and were included in the final synthesis. The review applies to a framework of three guiding questions: (1) What opportunities do AI technologies create for the economic empowerment of girls and women? (2) What are the social, technological, and system-level barriers that constrain women's and girls' access to, utilisation of, and benefits from AI for economic empowerment? and (3) What technical, policy and governance measures have been suggested or adopted to support an inclusive and gender-sensitive deployment of AI? The synthesis suggests that, although AI has great potential to contribute to women's economic empowerment, the prevailing gains are unevenly spread and frequently limited by structural inequalities and gaps in governance. The review highlights the importance of evidence-based, gender-responsive AI governance and strategic interventions to promote girls' and women's equitable economic outcomes.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Women's Economic Empowerment; Gender Equality; Digital Inclusion

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the significant manifestation of Fourth Industrial Revolution (FIR) as it can be widely utilised in military, industry, economy, science and technology, medical treatment, education and service industry. It is believed that AI will open up endless innovation and new industrial revolution, which will change human life greatly (Abdelbary & Shreaf, 2024). As the world is undergoing fast changes of technology and transformation mainly influenced by the FIR, AI and robotics (increasing use of them) will be the centre of progressing and growing in the future years. Khanum *et al.* (2020) hypothesised that women's economic empowerment is essential for sustainable development as the path toward the mainstream development of sustainable development process in any country would remain unpaved without their participation in common development schemes. The United Nations (UN) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) highlight that the ability to make choices is a core component of women's empowerment (WE), which in turn promotes gender equality and inclusivity (Abera, 2023; Dhiman, 2023). Among the projects considered capable of affording women greater control over

their lives and professional work is that of empowering women (Cakranegara *et al.*, 2022). Complete respect, self-reliance and a happy and content life are what empowerment all means to these people. Thus, by enabling women to become professionals in their field they will be able to live up to their full potential (Lee *et al.*, 2023)

In addition, WE enable women to manage their own financial resources; protect their families; improve their own education and that of their children; contribute to the workforce; and reduce household poverty substantially (Muchomba, 2021). WE is examined in terms of six broad dimensions; economic, social, political, physical, legal and psychological. They reflect how women value themselves, their ability to make decisions, their access to resources and opportunities, their right to have a say in matters that affect their lives (in the home as well as beyond it), and their ability to undertake social actions that bring about a more just social and economic order at a national and transnational level (Akeju, *et al.*, 2024). AI has transformed the way people live, work, and play. The potential for promoting economic growth, advancing health outcomes, and transforming education is immense. Yet the benefits of AI have not been evenly distributed, and girls and women are frequently at the losing end. Although the transformative power of AI is not debatable, the distribution of its associated benefits is uneven, which poses fundamental questions about whether such technologies advance or undermine women's empowerment. Therefore, this systematic review holistically examines the degree to which AI technologies influence the economic empowerment of girls and women while taking into account the potential opportunities and risks, and the policy actions required to ensure that AI is leveraged for inclusive, gender-equitable development.

Research Questions

The review was structured around the following guiding questions:

- 1) What opportunities do AI technologies create for the economic empowerment of girls and women?
- 2) What are the social, technological, and system-level barriers that constrain women's and girls' access to, utilisation of, and benefits from AI for economic empowerment?
- 3) What technical, policy and governance measures have been suggested or adopted to support an inclusive and gender-sensitive deployment of AI?

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence

In the field of computer science, AI, is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems (Drukker *et al.*, 2020). AI is already a part of everyday life, behind the scenes of technologies like facial recognition, speech recognition in virtual assistants (Amazon Alexa, Apple's Siri, Google Assistant and Microsoft Cortana) and even driverless cars (Kumar & Agarwal, 2025). The term AI was authored and defined by John McCarthy at the time as the science and engineering of making intelligent machines (Collins, *et al.*, 2021). AI and Robotics, Web3, Blockchain, Cloud computing, Quantum computing, Internet of Things (IoT), 3D Printing, Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality, Biotechnologies, are some of the most leading technologies in the application of the fourth industrial revolution (4IR) and are very popular within human activities (Ojokheta & Omokhabi, 2023). These tools allow authors to create polished cohesive work more rapidly which is especially useful in settings with limited time (Ajiye & Omokhabi, 2025)

The types of intelligence include cognitive, emotional and social intelligence, AI can be divided into analytical AI, human-inspired AI, and humanised AI (Helmiatin *et al.*, 2024). Besides, AI

may be classified into different evolutionary stages such as artificial narrow intelligence (ANI), artificial general intelligence (AGI) and artificial super intelligence (ASI) (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). AI maybe the widely viewed as machines being able to perform tasks that would require intelligence if a human was to execute it (Schoser, 2023). Along with the narrow interpretation of AI presented above, there are some other definitions that have been developed in the literature, which to some extent, combine the disciplines of psychology with that of computer science; Goertzel (2010), Chollet (2019), Wang (2022), and Legg and Hutter (2007b).

First, Goertzel (2010) described AI as being capable of identifying patterns that can be measured through observable sequences of actions or responses. Second, Chollet (2019) defined a system's intelligence as the extent to which it is able to efficiently acquire skills over a range of tasks, given priors, experience, and generalization difficulty. At the background of Chollet (2019) definition is learning (skill acquisition), following that, Wang (2022) described intelligence as the capacity of an information processing system to adapt to its environment on the basis of processing in the presence of uncertainty about the environment. Then, in a paper on defining machine intelligence, Legg and Hutter (2007b) give this definition of intelligence an agent's ability to attain goals in a broad class of environments.

Women Empowerment

WE is necessary to promote women's health claim (Cohen & Richards, 1994). Over the past two decades WE has become the main focus of international development initiatives. When 189 countries joined the Millennium Development Goals in 2000 they committed to promoting WE and gender equality (Shaw,2006). Women's empowerment has become a key focus of global development initiatives (Upadhyay *et al.* 2014). At the Cairo Conference three main facets of WE were emphasised: lowering gender inequality, advancing health and providing access to financial resources. There are many definitions of the general term empowerment but most of them centre on Sen's (1989) ideas and refer to a process of change, ability and choice. WE according to Kabeer (2012) is a transformational process that teaches those who have been denied the capacity to make decisions how to do so according to earlier theories this definition is accurate. According to Narayan (2002) the mechanisms that promote empowerment are information, access, accountability, inclusion and participation as well as local organisational capacity

Women Economic Empowerment

Women economic empowerment is a vital process for fostering gender equality, improving societal well-being, and driving sustainable economic growth (Cornish *et al.*, 2021; Stöckl *et al.*, 2021). At its core, it involves enabling women to participate equally in economic activities, access resources, and make decisions that impact their lives, families, and communities. The WE is one of the key aspect in world development and though women contribute a lot towards development, they are discriminated against, more so in the developing nations. Women made contribution to community resilience through agriculture and food security,value chain, health and nutrition, home management, traditional elderly, care, and rural companies,while rural women faced social and economic injustices and the barriers of gender discrimination, illiteracy; and scarce access to technology to upgrade their roles as agents of change in rural communities (Omokabi & Fajimi,2023).Women , too, are subjected to worse treatment than men under the rules, norms, customs and character of society. This unjustified mindset against women marginalised them in social, cultural, religious, financial and legal aspect. (Andriamahery & Qamruzzaman, 2021). This process involves multiple dimensions including equal access to

education, job opportunities, economic means, liberty of movement and engagement in decision-making at the household, community and political arenas.

In the general context, empowered women contribute significantly to economic and social progress. Desai *et al.* (2024) submitted that financial literacy and entrepreneurial orientation are significant contributors to financial well-being, proxy for economic empowerment. Cardona *et al.* (2024) study assessed two dimensions of women's economic empowerment, the first aspect, decision making at the household level, was assessed by women's ability to decide on household purchases of large items, daily needs, medical treatment, and clothes. This dimension was feasible and reliable across all contexts. The second component, economic autonomy, was approximated by women's possession of a savings, knowledge of where to get financial information, and financial goals.

Ranabahu and Tanima (2022) demonstrate that while microfinance services enable women entrepreneurship, it also worsens exclusion and further marginalisation. Women's agencies to access and use loans and engage in entrepreneurial activities, and therefore ultimately economic empowerment, are shaped by factors at the individual, household, institutional and community levels of structure and agency. Alayed and Alateeg, (2025) investigates the correlation between women's economic empowerment and social innovation through different aspects of empowerment such as decision-making at family level, freedom of mobility, participation in politics, having progressive attitudes and parental background. These findings highlight the significance of women's empowerment in these areas as a means to stimulate innovative activities in the community and in particular, supporting women's autonomy, involvement in politics, and holding progressive attitudes among women. WE encompass several critical dimensions among the multiple aspects of empowerment include freedom of movement and household decision-making as the key factors that influence women empowerment. Progressive attitude and autonomy at parental house are two of the next most significant predictors of women empowerment whereas political participation turned out to be the lowest predictor (Das, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This review used a systematic review method to compile the current empirical and theoretical literature on the impact of AI technologies on the economic empowerment of girls and women. The review was conducted in line with the PRISMA 2020 statement to promote transparency, reproducibility, and rigour in the method.

Eligibility Criteria

A set of inclusion and exclusion criteria was defined before searching.

Inclusion Criteria

Population: Girls and women of any age group.

Intervention/Exposure: Artificial intelligence applications (for example., machine learning, automation, algorithms, predictive analytics, robotics, natural language processing).

Outcomes: Economic empowerment (for example employment, entrepreneurship, financial inclusion, income generation, education, healthcare, agriculture, digital skills, access to credit).

Study Type: Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, policy reports, NGO/IGO reports with systematic evidence.

Time frame: 2010–2025 (period of rapid AI diffusion).

Language: English.

Exclusion Criteria

- Articles not addressing AI specifically (for example general ICT or digital technology without AI components).
- Studies not linking AI to economic outcomes for girls and women.
- Commentaries, editorials, or opinion pieces without evidence.
- Duplicates and non-English publications.

Search Strategy: A comprehensive and structured search was conducted across multidisciplinary databases. Databases Searched : Scopus ,Web of Science , Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Xplore, Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) Digital Library PubMed,Google Scholar (supplementary search) and UN Women, World Bank, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), International Telecommunication Union (ITU), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) policy repositories .

Search Terms

Boolean operators and controlled vocabulary were used: AI terms: artificial intelligence OR machine learning OR algorithm OR automation OR robotics OR AI OR predictive analytics, Gender terms: women OR girls OR female OR gender, Economic empowerment terms: economic empowerment OR employment OR entrepreneurship OR financial inclusion OR digital skills OR labour market OR income OR workforce and Combined search string (example): artificial intelligence OR machine learning OR algorithm OR automation) and (women OR girls OR female OR gender) AND (economic empowerment OR employment OR entrepreneurship OR financial inclusion)

A PRISMA flow diagram was created to document the number of studies identified, screened, excluded, and included.

1. Identification

- Records identified: 1,100
- After duplicates removed: 820
→ Duplicates removed = 280

2. Screening

- Records screened: 820

3. Records excluded: 350

→ Records moving to full text = $820 - 350 = 470$

4. Eligibility

- Full-text assessed: 470
- Full-text excluded: 385
Studies remaining = $470 - 385 = 85$

5. Included

- Studies included in qualitative synthesis: 85
- Studies included in quantitative synthesis: 0
- **Total studies included in final review: 49**

Ethical Considerations

Since this study was a review and analysis of existing data, it did not require an ethics application. Ethical principles of transparency, honest reporting and non-bias were adhered to throughout.

learning, automating administrative duties, and providing real time analytics, AI is making it seem like it can solve age-old disparities in access to quality education and in equity of educational outcomes (Holmes, Bialik & Fadel, 2021). In spite of some big strides, girls in many states on the continent still encounter systemic obstacles to accessing education, including poverty, early marriage, socio-cultural norms, and inadequate infrastructure (UNESCO,2023). In with the times and imperative, the convergence of AI and gender equity in African education is not only timely but a necessity. Recent research has examined how AI-supported classrooms might provide focused interventions, such as adaptive learning platforms and intelligent tutoring systems, to aid marginalised students, with a particular focus on girls (Ugwu, Aimola, & Rita, 2025). These are interventions that can be adjusted to fill learning gaps and can provide multilingual support making them inclusive solutions for learning through digital means. Sex differences of access to education have been the subject of extensive reports in Africa (UNESCO,2023) However, AI comes with an array of tools to help bridge these gap in equity by delivering adaptive learning materials that are tailored to the learning speed of girls within their own context as well as their socio cultural and other challenges.

AI offers tremendous, latent potential for educational reformers to bring benefit to under resourced environments, especially in the Least Developed Countries where the need to improve access to quality learning is the greatest (Hakimi, Shahidzay, & Kohistan, 2024). These systems not only enhance accessibility but also address individual learning needs, an essential factor in empowering marginalised groups. Notably, results consist of equal gender participation in the enrolment, strong reliability and validity indicators, greater mobile learning, technology adoption rate among the female participants, the infrastructure availability and the present measures considered as a positive factor, the curriculum is moderately infused with those measures, and the accessibility is generally perceived as adequate (Quraishi *et al.*, 2024). E-learning provides flexibility in terms of time and access to various resources and uses novel teaching methods. Cloud-based solutions have been effective during disruption such as the COVID-19 pandemic, enabling education to continue with little disruption. E-learning promotes autonomy in learning and digital literacy (Musawi *et al.*, 2025).

Alshraah *et al.*, (2024) research focused on investigating the role of online learning, digital literacy, and AI systems in addressing the issue of low quality of education and barriers related to gender differences in Saudi Arabia in light of the Kingdom's Vision 2030. Results show a significant part (55.68%) of them have access to quality education (56.73%), applying digital devices in education, encouragingly, 84.95% realize the role of digital literacy and online education in opening up education. Ebrahimi, *et al* (2025) submitted that as e-learning expands, AI provides transformational opportunities to increase access to education, engage learners and disrupt old barriers. A cross-sectional study was carried out among 110 female students from the medical, computer science, education, and economics courses with findings indicating that AI greatly improves access to education and incentive for female students. AI technologies have enabled flexible, personalised, and accessible educational environments, especially for female learners in a distance university, AI- based e-learning tools influenced learning outcomes, engagement and brought about improvements in accessibility and inclusivity (Ahmadi *et al.*,2024). With its potential for creative responses to the specific challenges women face, AI could enable women and promote gender equality and learning and education materials for girls and women (Patil *et al.*,2024).

AI for Entrepreneurship and Business Growth

AI-based learning solutions enhance skills, giving women entrepreneurs the skills to manoeuvre flexible business environments. Moreover, AI-based market analytics delivers richer customer insights, allowing customised services and business growth (Almheiri, Chopra, & Haddad, 2025). There is a potential for AI to give rise to new business opportunities for entrepreneurs (Shepherd & Majchrzak, 2022), but it can also force people into self-employment when their existing wage work gets automated with the adoption of AI. So too in the effects it has directly on the formation and advancement of entrepreneurship, AI technologies have been construed as externally based enablers and facilitators of entrepreneurship (Davidsson *et al.*, 2020; Davidsson & Sufyan, 2023). AI-based innovators exploit and create new business opportunities, and AI can reduce costs such as labour cost (by automation) and capital cost (by fintech services). Because they can predict, AI systems can potentially address problems of uncertainty, and by doing so, open new avenues for entrepreneurial action (Townsend & Hunt, 2019). AI has particularly significant implications for how entrepreneurs develop, design, and scale their ventures in the process of entrepreneurship (Chalmers *et al.*, 2021). Like any radical innovation, AI can empower entrepreneurs and open up new windows of opportunity to introduce new products or services through entrepreneurial activities (Obschonka & Audretsch, 2020). In addition, contributions concerning AI methodologies may benefit the entrepreneurial decision-making systems such that the quality of decisions on their effectiveness and efficiency is improved, and in turn, the performance of operations is enhanced (Kraus *et al.*, 2020). In addition, AI can not only play a leading role in driving the transformation and upgrading of AI enterprises themselves, but also inspire more traditional companies to use AI solutions to develop their business models.

AI in Healthcare and Wellbeing for Girls and Women

Most frequent usage for AI and machine learning (ML)-based methods in the pregnancy field were in prenatal care for example foetal anomalies, placental functioning, perinatal care, birth and delivery and preterm birth. Translation of AI into clinical care is being targeted by clinical decision support systems and mobile health applications, all in all, ML and AI methods, including the state of the art deep learning (DL), methods are increasingly used to improve the pregnancy outcome (Davidson & Boland, 2021). Among the mobile application focused on women's health and wellness is the Flo app (by Flo Health Inc). Using AI, Flo provides its users with predictions for their periods and ovulation and lets them track their periods, fertile window, ovulation and symptoms while trying to conceive or avoid pregnancy, and even track pregnancy symptoms and foetal development. Aside from its tracking features, Flo also delivers evidence-based and expert reviewed educational content, accessible through the in-app library (Zhaunova *et al.*, 2023). AI-enabled mammography screening alongside radiologists led to the detection of 20% more cancers-achieved a similar cancer detection rate as standard double reading, with a markedly lower screen-reading workload, suggesting that implementation of AI in mammography screening is safe (Lang *et al.*, 2023). ML techniques are a reasonable tool to enhance the prediction of adverse outcomes in pregnant women at high risk for preeclampsia. (Schmidt, *et al.*, 2022). AI is revolutionising the world including the domain of healthcare, more specifically in women's healthcare. AI has the potential to dramatically reduce these differences by providing personalised, immediate and cost-effective services for reproductive health, in the domain of family planning the most popular application is fertility tracking, Wearable technology with AI-based models are increasingly applied also in continuous maternal health monitoring (Omokhabi *et al.*, 2025). AI applications in women's health could transform prevention, detection and management of diseases (Korytnikova, 2023).

AI for Agricultural Productivity (for rural women)

Recently, various crop genetics, fertilisation and AI-driven field management would contribute to higher crop production (Luo *et al.*, 2023). Some of the far-reaching advantages of the AI-based systems are yield prediction with higher accuracy and also the AI enabled irrigation system promotes better and smart usage of resources such as water and electricity (Sinwar *et al.*, 2020). Variable Rate Irrigation (VRI) represents an innovative irrigation technique which supplies variable amounts of water between different areas according to their needs in an irrigation event (Balafoutis *et al.*, 2017). It may be done with a self-propelled machine or through micro-irrigation. Popular systems are to apply Mid Elevation Spray Application (MESA) Efficiency = 85 %. An irrigation efficiency of 87.97 % was recorded when compared to the old traditional method while growing Geranium psilostemon in the work of Ercan Oğuztürk *et al.*, (2025) highlighting the use of a smart irrigation system to optimise water usage effectively. Preite and Vignali (2024) also reported that a 27 % water saving and a 57 % energy saving were obtained by applying a multi-layer perceptron neural network. Today many organisations are working towards building new and harmful technologies such as IoT which is being used for effective farm management. These technologies remove inefficiencies associated with them and contribute to maximising results and changes in their fields. Farmers employing AI technologies such as IOT, mobile apps, and sensors to know their fields like the temperature, water needs, weather and more. Smart agriculture proved to be a very promising solution to increase the capacity of food production in an environment-friendly way with good food safety and quality. Smart farming is a major contributor to SDG 2 by promoting a more profitable, resilient and sustainable agri-food system (Musa & Basir, 2021)

Research Question 2: What are the social, technological, and system-level barriers that constrain women's and girls' access to, utilisation of, and benefits from AI for economic empowerment?

Recent studies have shown that women use generative AI (genAI) chatbots less frequently than men, with women engaging with AI in fewer domains and adopting a more critical approach (Gesser-Edelsburg *et al.*, 2024). Women also express more concerns about the potential loss of independent thinking (Stöhr *et al.*, 2024). Møgelvang *et al.* (2024) also stated that women may be disadvantaged in the workforce due to a lack of experience with AI tools. The social implications of this coupled with digital divide and gender stereotypes for the technology-related roles in part dictates the barriers of women in the uptake of AI in higher education (Ahn *et al.*, 2022). Women are also disadvantaged compared to men when it comes to access to technology and digital resources, (United Nations (UN) Women, 2022). The result of a digital divide and entrenched gendered social attitudes towards technology-related roles leads to obstacles for women to use AI in higher education (Ahn *et al.*, 2022).

One important dimension of the digital divide is the gender digital divide, which illustrates the systemic obstacles that women encounter when trying to access information and communication technologies (ICTs). These obstacles severely curtail women's access to AI resources and tools, limiting their opportunities to use technology for growth, whether personal or professional (Peláez-Sánchez, & Glasserman-Morales, 2023). The world has been changed by the digital revolution, providing enormous possibilities for developing economically, socially, and educationally while digitalisation is gender-neutral, it has led to gender inequality within its users (ICT users) or the digital gender divide which denies access to information use and networking opportunities to women (Roy *et al.*, 2024). As AI and automation become more prevalent, digital technologies are now more integral than ever to the everyday lives of people in education, at work, and in

community life. But uneven access to these technologies compounds existing social inequalities, resulting in digital divides along the lines of socio-economic status, race, gender, and place of residence (Lahiri, 2024).

Research Question 3: What technical, policy and governance measures have been suggested or adopted to support an inclusive and gender-sensitive deployment of AI?

Policies, practices and interventions can contribute towards the mitigation of gendered disparities arising from AI tools. These broadly fall into two groups: technical and non-technical. The former relates to the algorithm and the data used to train them and the LLMs, and the latter relates to the legal framework and related state policies (Dobrevá *et al.*, 2023). Various gender bias mitigation techniques and frameworks have been suggested either for data bias, algorithmic bias or bias detection frameworks (Shrestha & Das, 2022). Algorithms effect assessments and audits should be created during the design and development of AI products and services and should extend to the training process with data. Mökander (2023) stresses the need to interweave technology-oriented audits with process-oriented audits into comprehensive procedures for auditing not only how AI systems are designed and implemented, but also how they effect users and societies in practice over time.

The AI industry and developers should be urged to: use diverse and inclusive data sets to reflect diverse genders, cultures, and perspectives; develop industry standards and policies; establish ongoing monitoring and evaluation for systemic biases in AI; have AI models (and especially interactive applications) qualitatively evaluated from the user perspective in collaboration with a range of external and independent parties (such as human rights organizations, gender experts, affected users); conduct deep human rights and risk assessments, with special consideration for vulnerable groups; release ‘risk cards’ that represent the performance of AI applications; adopt good practice in hiring and promotion within the AI industry and create new organisational cultures; run training & mentoring schemes to redress gender imbalance. Strong regulatory, legal and government policy frameworks for the development, use and management of AI and AI-related activity can contribute to addressing risk emanating from gendered bias in AI (UNESCO 2020;2024). UNESCO (2020, 2024) urges governments and policymakers to establish standards for data gathering and algorithm development that minimise biases being introduced or reinforced; disseminate the attributes, contexts and output characteristics for which AI models need to provide equal performance; establish monitoring systems and carry out periodic audits to monitor rights and ethics-compliance of AI systems, require technology companies to fund research on the effects of AI on various populations and support, AI solutions that address the needs and experiences of women, and that do not contain bias or adversely affect them. The UN General Assembly took the 2024 step to promote safe, secure and trustworthy” AI systems, calling on member states to mainstream a disability, gender and racial equality perspective in policy-making and the policy instruments that support it (UN, 2024). UN Women (2024) recommendations highlight the need for strong gender mainstreaming throughout all the elements of the Global Digital Compact package of measures, including within the areas of: the right to be free from technology- facilitated gender-based violence and discrimination, equal access to education and economic opportunities, equal voice, leadership and participation.

Conclusion

This systematic review proves that the AI technologies are both transformative opportunities and potential risks for the economic empowerment of girls and women. AI can also create new types of jobs, entrepreneurship and financial inclusion; increase productivity; and reduce barriers to

entry in traditionally male-dominated industries. However, in the absence of intentional efforts to the contrary, AI systems are likely to exacerbate existing gender disparities via biased data, exclusionary design processes, uneven access to digital infrastructure, and labour market disruptions that disproportionately harm women.

The analysis highlights that the barriers to girls' and women's participation and success are not just about technology but about deep-seated socio-economic and institutional factors. Gaps in digital skills, direct representation in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and AI-related fields, unpaid care burdens, and weak legal protections intersect with AI deployment to limit women's economic gains. Tackling these issues, then, calls for more than techno solutions, it requires harmonious governance responses that fold gender equality considerations into the design of AI and its diffusion. Policy and governance avenues are pivotal in contributing to inclusive AI futures. Gender-responsive regulation, ethical AI frameworks, targeted education and skills programmes and support for women-led innovation can ensure that AI serves to, rather than hinders, women's economic empowerment. Equally important is the active involvement of women and girls in AI development, decision-making and governance to ensure systems are shaped around diverse needs and experiences. With AI development progressing, ongoing focus on equity, inclusion and accountability will be necessary to realising its potential as a means of fostering gender-equitable economic growth.

Recommendations

Legislation and technical solutions tend to generalise women as a group, without considering the social context and the cultural factors that shape women's lives and possibilities worldwide. From a socio-cultural standpoint, UNESCO, OECD and Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) (2022) highlighted the effects of AI on women's working lives and suggested that;

- 1) Governments, working with education providers, employers, and technology developers, need to encourage and support women's engagement in STEM education and place focus on reskilling and upskilling women workers whose livelihoods are disrupted due to labour market impacts of AI. Policies and programmes should be tailored to the local context, taking into account cultural, social and economic variations within and across countries and sectors, as AI influence women's work lives in ever-diversifying ways. Governments and business leaders should also actively work to challenge and remove gender biases in the development, implementation, and regulation of AI systems and in creating equal, diverse, and safe workplaces that enable women to participate fully and advance in AI-enabled work.
- 2) In this regard, UNESCO (2020, 2024) urges Member States to actively and collectively work on combating gender bias and discrimination in AI. This also includes the raising of public awareness by means of targeted actions such as education programmes, training activities or public learning campaigns which contribute to better understanding of the effects and consequences of gender-based discrimination in AI systems. UNESCO also calls on States to create sustainable funding schemes and open pathways for girls and women to access AI education and training, and advance diversity, equity and inclusion in hiring, employment and related policy-contexts.
- 3) UNESCO (2020, 2024) once again emphasises that human rights-based principles should be respected by governments and technology companies in the design, development, use and regulation of AI systems. This can be achieved only with the incorporation of gender-responsive and intersectional ethical approaches, with strong mechanisms for identification and mitigation of bias that promote inclusivity, accountability, transparency, and fairness

within and through AI applications. UNESCO also advises that AI strategies and regulations transcend single-axis understandings of discrimination and employ a full intersectional analysis of (dis)abilities and other converging forms of inequalities. It is a perspective that acknowledges power relations inherent in intersecting identities related to race, age, gender, disability, ethnicity and other social markers. An intersectional lens for developing AI policy is crucial to support contextually-relevant, participatory and transformative governance, as well as for the pursuit of algorithmic justice and fair results for all.

- 4) Governments and regional policy-making institutions should mainstream gender at all stages of law- and policy-making, starting with the generation, collection and utilisation of data for policy formulation. This involves a systematic commitment to gender-disaggregate data and to apply intersectional analysis where appropriate, and to organise, monitor and publicly report reliable statistics on participation, access, and outcomes throughout the policy life cycle. In the spirit of promoting evidence-based decisions and accountability, the governments may leverage internationally validated measurement frameworks such as the African Union (AU) Gender Scorecard Index, the UNDP Gender and Development Index and the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Index and adapt these tools as required at the national and sectoral levels. This approach defines a challenge and a mandate to realise gender equality and women's empowerment.
- 5) Governments, together with the educational institutions and the private industry, should create specialised funds and delivery mechanisms to grow opportunities to learn about AI for girls and women. This should include the establishment of focused scholarships, grants and fellowships in AI and related fields, consistent with the commitments to diversity, equity and inclusion in hiring and workforce policies. Governments should also enable funding for and subsidise AI training courses and professional certifications to allow for a cost-effective scale-up. In addition, public-private partnerships among governments, educators, and industry to further expand access to quality AI education for marginalised and underrepresented groups should be encouraged, guaranteeing inclusive participation in the AI ecosystem.

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